

ENSURING THE EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION AND GETTING OUT OF POVERTY THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7410235>

Abstract. *The article clearly shows what indicators are used to assess the level of poverty in our country and ways to reduce it. Also, organizational and economic mechanisms and directions of poverty reduction are also considered in it.*

Keywords: *poverty, poverty reduction, poverty rate, poverty assessment, consumption basket reflected.*

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Аннотация. *В статье наглядно показано, какие показатели используются для оценки уровня бедности в нашей стране и пути ее снижения. Также в ней рассмотрены организационно-экономические механизмы и направления сокращения бедности.*

Ключевые слова: *бедность, сокращение бедности, уровень бедности, оценка бедности, отраженная потребительская корзина.*

Introduction

Global poverty is one of the major problems, the causes and consequences of which are not limited to the solution of one country. Efforts to improve the standard of living and stabilize the life of the population groups suffering from poverty and its consequences, and to provide them with the necessary conditions, have become one of the urgent issues in the focus of the world community. In the conditions of rapidly growing socio-economic development, the level of poverty among certain sections of the population is increasing day by day. In particular, 10% of the world's population, that is, 700 mln. people make up the population of African and Asian countries. 17.2% of them are rural residents. The fact that poverty cannot be completely eliminated even by ensuring the employment of the population, according to estimates, 8% of the working population lives in poverty indicates that the socio-economic situation in African and Asian countries is not good [1].

In 2015, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the "Goals in the field of sustainable development" and put forward the goals of further strengthening the principles of peace, prosperous life and justice in the world that is on the threshold of the new millennium. The main goal of this Declaration is to "gradually eliminate all forms of poverty" by 2030 [2]. Measures to significantly improve the lives of more than 100 million people in the world living in economically backward settlements until 2020 have been launched [3].

Analysis of literature on the topic

The experience of the countries of the world shows that the role of small business and private entrepreneurship is extremely important in reducing poverty. Because it is this sector that provides services for the creation of new jobs. Its role in the production of some necessary and integral products for large enterprises, in the development of new types of goods and services, in reducing the costs of production of goods, and in increasing the volume of production of

competitive and export products is increasing. In the United States alone, 55% of the innovations implemented in recent decades were created in the small business sector [4]. Therefore, according to the economist L. Gurov, small business determines the rate of economic growth, helps in the effective distribution of material, financial and personnel resources, creates jobs, requires much less cost than large enterprises in the creation of new workplaces [5]. In particular, entities operating in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship are exempted from profit tax, loans and financial assistance are provided to them in a preferential way, and this was achieved by using the scientific and technical potential.

Research methodology

Explaining the main characteristics of small business and entrepreneurial activity in reducing poverty, explaining the issues related to poverty, its definition and reduction. During the research, monographic observation, systematic approach, analysis and synthesis methods were used.

Analysis and results

Researches show that in order to determine the criterion of poverty, first of all, it is required to determine the legal basis of the "consumption basket". Determining and introducing the "consumption basket" and "minimum of living", which are important in determining the amount of allowances and pensions, and clarifying the indicators and norms of these indices, which are the basis of the domestic policy of each state, has become a vital necessity. It is known that in determining the standard of living of the population, the concept of "consumption basket" is used, that is, a set of goods and services that provide a certain level of consumption. In international practice, there are statistical, sociological, resource, and normative methods for calculating the living wage. The composition of the minimum living wage is set differently in different countries. For example, the "consumer basket" includes 300 goods and services in the USA, 475 goods in Germany, 350 goods and services in England, and 156 goods and services in Russia. "Consumption basket" can be divided into three main components - food, non-food and services. The percentage of food in it determines the standard of living of the population.

The majority of the population in our country has a higher demand for food products in the "consumer basket". In order to eliminate this share and increase the amount of non-food products and services in the "consumer basket", a number of tasks were set before the relevant organizations and institutions. In this, the main attention was focused on training the population in entrepreneurship, effective use of existing opportunities. For the same purpose, the most effective way to increase the population's income should be to get the citizens out of the state and mood of poverty, ensure their employment, and direct them to entrepreneurship.

Based on the "growth point" of each neighborhood, leading businessmen and mayor's assistants help to implement new projects, develop the types of services necessary for the daily needs of residents in the neighborhoods. It organizes the work of training the population, first of all, unemployed youth and women in professions and entrepreneurship, as well as ensuring their employment. A total of 13 trillion within the framework of "Each family is an entrepreneur", "Young people are our future" and other social programs aimed at attracting a large segment of the population to entrepreneurship and expanding their sources of income. More than 600,000 families were provided with preferential loans.

Conclusion

In order to reduce poverty, first of all, attention should be paid to reducing the unemployment rate. In this regard, conducting an active and effective policy that supports those who cannot help themselves independently, attracting the resources of the society and the private sector to these goals will have a great effect. In the conditions of modern development, a large part of the world's population lives in extreme poverty, even in the conditions of a severe shortage of food reserves and sources of income necessary to ensure the stable functioning of the human body. The level of poverty creates an acute shortage of essential supplies of food and drinking water security. These problems, in turn, increase the scope of social problems such as lack of access to services such as education, health care, social stigmatization and social isolation.

If the opportunities for the participation of the poor in production activities are expanded, this will also ensure their participation in the processes of economic growth as workers or entrepreneurs. For this, first of all, it is permissible to solve the problem of lack of necessary knowledge and skills.

It is appropriate to rely on foreign experience in reducing poverty in our country. The development of inclusive business models is especially important in this regard. It is appropriate to use China's experience in the development of private entrepreneurship and small business in the direction of poverty reduction.

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